

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Plasma miR-145-5p levels and risk of cancer-associated thrombosis—results from the HUNT study

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Abstract

Background: The incidence of cancer-associated venous thromboembolism (CAT) has risen in recent decades, underscoring the need for novel risk biomarkers and mechanistic insights. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) have emerged as promising biomarkers for various diseases, with elevated miRNA-145-5p (miR-145-5p) levels linked to reduced venous thromboembolism (VTE) risk. We aimed to investigate the association between plasma miR-145-5p levels and risk of future VTE related to (CAT) and unrelated to cancer (non-CAT).

Methods: Plasma miR-145-5p levels were measured in a case cohort derived from the Trøndelag Health Study (HUNT3; $N = 50\,807$). The study included 455 VTEs (95 CATs), occurring during 9 years of follow-up, and 1740 randomly sampled age-weighted subcohort participants. VTEs were classified as CAT if they occurred within 1 year before or 2 years after a cancer diagnosis. Multivariable adjusted hazard ratios (HRs) for CAT and non-CAT were estimated using weighted Cox regression, with cancer modeled as a time-varying covariate.

Results: Increasing miR-145-5p levels were associated with lower risk of CAT (HR per 1 SD, 0.70; 95% CI, 0.52-0.96) and non-CAT (HR, 0.81; 95% CI, 0.72-0.91). Individuals in the highest miR-145-5p quartile had lower risk of both CAT (HR, 0.55; 95% CI, 0.25-1.20) and non-CAT (HR, 0.48; 95% CI, 0.33-0.69) than those in the lowest quartile.

Conclusions: High plasma miR-145-5p levels were associated with lower risk of CAT and non-CAT, suggesting that miR-145-5p has the potential to serve as a risk biomarker for CAT.

KEYWORDS

biomarker, cancer, cohort studies, microRNAs, venous thromboembolism

1 | INTRODUCTION

Patients with cancer are known to have a 4- to 9-fold increased risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE) during the first year after cancer diagnosis [1,2], and 20 to 30% of all incident VTEs are related to

active cancer [2]. The incidence of cancer-associated VTE (CAT) has increased during the last decades [1], imposing a significant burden on both patients and health care systems. Compared with patients with VTE without active cancer, patients with VTE and with active cancer are more prone to VTE recurrence [3] and experience worse

outcomes, including increased mortality [4], greater morbidity [5,6], elevated bleeding risk during anticoagulant treatment [3], and prolonged hospital stays [7]. Several risk assessment models have been developed to identify patients with cancer at high VTE risk who would benefit from thromboprophylaxis [8,9], but their precision at the individual level has been insufficient [10,11]. Thus, there is a pressing need to discover novel biomarkers that can improve the precision of risk assessment and provide insight into the mechanisms driving CAT.

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small noncoding RNA molecules that regulate gene expression by inhibiting translation or degrading their target messenger RNAs [12]. Due to their stability in plasma [13], miRNAs have emerged as promising biomarkers for various diseases, including cancer [14] and VTE [15]. A review by Anijs et al. [16] highlighted the potential of miRNAs as prognostic biomarkers for CAT. However, the authors noted that inconsistencies among the reviewed studies, due to small sample sizes, varying study designs, and different blood sampling methods, necessitate larger population-based studies to explore the potential role of miRNAs as prognostic biomarkers for CAT [16].

Recently, we reported an inverse linear relationship between plasma miR-145-5p levels and VTE risk in a large case cohort derived from the general population [17]. Notably, individuals with the highest miR-145-5p levels had a 49% lower risk of first-lifetime VTE [17]. This epidemiological finding prompted an investigation into whether similar risk estimates extend to CAT, given the heterogeneous risk profiles and underlying mechanisms between VTE in patients with cancer and the general population [18,19]. miR-145-5p targets several key genes in the hemostatic system, including tissue factor (TF) [20], plasminogen activator inhibitor (PAI)-1 [21], and factor (F)XI [22], which are involved in pathways common to both cancer and VTE [23,24]. Therefore, we set out to investigate whether plasma miR-145-5p levels were associated with the risk of future CAT and VTE unrelated to cancer (non-CAT) leveraging data from a population-based case cohort.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study design and population

The Trøndelag Health Study (HUNT) is a cohort study comprising inhabitants of the former Nord-Trøndelag county in Norway [25]. From 2006 to 2008, all residents aged 20 years and above were invited to participate in the third survey of the HUNT Study (HUNT3), and 50 807 participated, accounting for 54% of those invited. Participants were followed up from enrollment until December 31, 2019, and all VTE events were recorded. The source cohort has been detailed previously [25]. From this source cohort, we created a case cohort in which the first 600 VTE events occurring during follow-up were included as cases (with the follow-up period concluding on August 31, 2015). This selection was

based on 2 main considerations: ensuring a robust sample size while maintaining the narrowest possible follow-up period to minimize the risk of regression dilution. After case selection, the subcohort was formed by randomly sampling 2000 participants from the entire cohort, weighted according to the age distribution among the cases, using 5-year age groups to ensure comparativeness. As incident CAT was the primary outcome of the study, the following exclusion criteria were applied to both the cases and the subcohort: previous VTE ($n = 56$), previous cancer ($n = 216$), missing plasma sample ($n = 99$), and missing miR-145-5p measurement ($n = 27$). We further excluded 20 VTE cases that occurred after the active cancer period (see Statistical Analysis section). After these exclusions, there were 95 cases and 208 subcohort members for the CAT analysis, and 340 cases and 1718 subcohort members for the non-CAT analyses. Due to the nature of the sampling, some cases were also included in the subcohort. Figure 1 depicts a flowchart of the study population. The regional committee for medical and health research ethics approved the study in agreement with the Helsinki Declaration, and all participants provided informed written consent.

2.2 | Data collection

Upon inclusion in the HUNT3 study, data were collected from all participants through physical examinations, self-administered questionnaires, and blood samples. Height and weight were recorded to the nearest centimeter and half-kilogram, respectively, with participants dressed without shoes and in light clothing. These measurements were used to calculate the body mass index (BMI) using the formula: $\text{weight}/\text{height}^2$. Information on history of arterial cardiovascular disease (CVD; yes/no) and daily smoking (yes/no) was extracted from self-reported questionnaires. Nonfasting blood samples were drawn into EDTA-containing vacutainer tubes to prevent coagulation. Plasma was separated by centrifugation at 3000g for 10 minutes and subsequently stored at -80°C in the HUNT Biobank, as described in detail elsewhere [26].

2.3 | miR-145-5p measurement

The plasma samples collected at inclusion in HUNT3 were retrieved from the HUNT Biobank and shipped on dry ice to QIAGEN Genomic Services. Total RNA was extracted with the miRNeasy Plasma Advanced Kit, reverse transcribed with the miRCURY LNA RT Kit, and miR-145-5p expression was measured by quantitative polymerase chain reaction using specific primers and SYBR green, along with reference genes and controls for extraction and retrotranscription efficiency. More details have been provided elsewhere [17].

FIGURE 1 Flowchart depicting the case-cohort study derived from the third survey of the Trøndelag Health Study (HUNT3). CAT cancer-associated VTE; VTE, venous thromboembolism. Created in BioRender. Antoun, C. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/wvyj2a>.

2.4 | Definition and validation of the outcome

The outcome of this study was incident VTE, which was characterized as CAT and non-CAT. CAT was defined as a VTE occurring within 1 year before or within 2 years after a cancer diagnosis. Previous studies have shown that the risk of VTE is highest during this period [27]. If a VTE event occurred in the absence of a cancer diagnosis, it was classified as non-CAT.

VTE cases were identified through hospital discharge diagnosis registries and autopsy records from the 3 hospitals serving the HUNT

study catchment area: Levanger hospital, Namsos hospital, and St. Olavs hospital in Trondheim. This process included an extensive search using relevant codes from the International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. A trained nurse conducted a thorough review of the medical records for each potential VTE case identified from the registries. VTE events were adjudicated and recorded when signs and symptoms of lower extremity deep vein thrombosis or pulmonary embolism were objectively confirmed by radiologic procedures or autopsy and treatment was initiated (unless contraindicated). In cases where a patient had concurrent pulmonary

embolism and deep vein thrombosis, the event was categorized as pulmonary embolism. VTE events were classified as either provoked or unprovoked. To make this classification, information on provoking factors within the 3 months preceding the event was extracted from medical records using standardized methods. The provoking factors included surgery, acute medical conditions (eg, stroke, myocardial infarction, and hospitalization for acute infections), trauma, immobilization, or other factors specifically described as provoking in the medical record.

Incident cancer diagnoses during follow-up were identified by linking participants' individual unique national civil registration numbers to the Cancer Registry of Norway. Since 1951, cancer registration and reporting have been mandatory by law in Norway. The registry receives information from various medical sources, including general practitioners, hospital physicians, pathology laboratories, and death certificates, and included information about the date of cancer diagnosis (reflecting the date of clinical diagnosis), the stage of cancer at diagnosis (local, regional, or distant metastasis), and the localization of cancer [28]. The registry has a completeness rate of 98.8%, with 94% of diagnoses being histologically confirmed [28].

2.5 | Statistical analysis

The plasma levels of miR-145-5p was normalized against levels of miR-425-5p for each individual using the Delta-Delta Cycle threshold method ($\Delta\Delta Ct$). The choice of the normalizer was based on stability assessments using the geNorm and BestKeeper algorithms. The normalized levels of miR-145-5p were divided into quartiles (Q) based on the distribution of those values in the subcohort. Given that previous studies have reported sex differences in plasma miR-145-5p levels [17,29], which could lead to residual confounding even after adjusting for sex, quartiles were calculated separately for each sex within the subcohort and then combined to reconvene the full data set. Participants' characteristics at baseline, at cancer diagnosis, and at VTE diagnosis were summarized using mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median with interquartile range (IQR) for continuous variables, and percentages for categorical variables. The baseline characteristics were also summarized for each miR-145-5p quartile separately.

To evaluate the association between plasma miR-145-5p levels and the risk of CAT and non-CAT, participants were followed up from their inclusion date in the study until the earliest occurrence of 1 of the following: VTE diagnosis, migration out of the county or country, death, or the end of follow-up on August 31, 2015. Cox proportional hazard models were used to calculate hazard ratios (HRs) with 95% CIs according to miR-145-5p levels for CAT and non-CAT. Cancer status was included in the Cox model as a time-varying covariate. Participants who had a cancer diagnosis contributed person-time as cancer-exposed only during the active cancer period (defined as 1 year prior to diagnosis through 2 years after diagnosis) and contributed person-time as cancer free before this period. As some

VTEs occurred after the defined active cancer period among participants with cancer, they could not be reliably classified as CAT or non-CAT. Thus, to avoid potential misclassification, individuals diagnosed with cancer who did not develop CAT were censored at the end of their active cancer period. Due to this censoring, 20 VTE events never entered the analyses (ie, the total number of VTE cases included in our analyses were 435, rather than 455). Figure 2 illustrates how the person time was calculated, taking into account all different scenarios. HRs were estimated using model 1 (adjusted for age and sex) and model 2 (model 1+ BMI and arterial cardiovascular disease). BMI was missing for 15 of the participants, and the missingness was handled with complete-case analysis. For participants with active cancer, model 3 included cancer site and stage in addition to the variables in model 2. To mitigate overfitting, given the expected limited number of CAT events, we reduced the dimensionality by grouping cancer sites into 3 VTE-risk categories (low, intermediate, and high) (Supplementary Table S1), and dichotomizing stage as localized vs nonlocalized. The VTE-risk categorization was informed by risk estimates for individual cancer sites reported in a prior large population-based study [1]. Sites with HRs in the lowest tertile (≤ 33 rd percentile) were classified as low, those in the highest tertile (≥ 67 th percentile) as high, and the remainder as intermediate. This approach limits degrees of freedom while preserving key VTE-relevant information. For transparency, HRs from the model retaining the full categorical detail for cancer site and stage were also reported.

To account for the case-cohort design, the Cox Model for Case-Cohort Data with Stratified Subcohort-Selection R package (*cchs*) was used to fit the Cox models [30]. The Cox models were weighted according to the sampling distribution of the subcohort and stratified by age bands defined in the overall cohort (<50, 50-59, 60-69, 70-79, and ≥ 80 years). HRs for CAT and non-CAT were estimated according to 2 modelling approaches for miR-145-5p: (1) per 1-SD increase in standardized levels (z-score; mean, 0; SD, 1) and (2) across quartiles (with lowest quartile as reference). We used those 2 approaches to avoid imposing an overly a priori functional form given the novelty of this study. The continuous modeling approach was motivated by prior spline analyses, suggesting an approximately linear association, and by its greater efficiency, particularly given the expected limited number of CAT events. The quartile modeling approach was included to probe potential nonlinearity and threshold effects, especially for the CAT outcome, and to facilitate comparison with prior work that reported quartile-based estimates. P_{trend} was obtained from a Wald test of the quartile variable entered as an ordinal term.

To allow for the evaluation of the proportional hazard assumption, we extended the *cchs* R package. The R script for this extension is provided as Supplementary File 1. The assessment followed the methods detailed previously [31], with the proportional hazard assumption considered violated if any of the 3 correlation tests—event time, rank event time, or Kaplan–Meier estimates—produced a P value of $<.05$. All Cox models met the proportional hazards assumption.

FIGURE 2 Visual illustration of the different observational periods based on exposure to cancer and the classification of the outcome as CAT or non-CAT.

- Scenario A: Participants without cancer who did not develop VTE during follow-up. These participants are censored only at the end of the follow-up period.
- Scenario B: Participants without cancer who developed VTE during follow-up. The time from study inclusion to the VTE event is counted as exposure-free person-time, while the period after the VTE event is censored.
- Scenario C: Participants with cancer who did not develop VTE. These participants are censored at the end of the active cancer period.
- Scenario D: Similar to Scenario C, but the VTE event occurs after censoring and is therefore not included.
- Scenario E: Participants diagnosed with VTE after their cancer diagnosis and within the active cancer period. These participants contribute exposed person-time, and the VTE is classified as CAT.
- Scenario F: Participants whose VTE diagnosis occurred before their cancer diagnosis but during the active cancer period. The VTE is classified as CAT, and they contribute exposed person-time starting one year before their cancer diagnosis until the VTE event, after which they are censored.
- Scenario G: Participants whose VTE diagnosis occurred before their cancer diagnosis and outside the active cancer period. These participants contribute exposure-free person-time up to the VTE event.

CAT cancer-associated VTE; VTE, venous thromboembolism.

TABLE 1 Baseline characteristics of the subcohort that remained cancer free during the entire follow-up period and those who had cancer diagnosis, overall and in quartiles (Q) of miR-145-5p levels.

Characteristic	All	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Cancer free					
<i>n</i>	1440	374	356	363	347
Age (y)	64.0 ± 13.9	63.6 ± 14.1	63.2 ± 13.2	63.5 ± 13.6	65.9 ± 14.6
Sex (female)	58 (829)	57 (212)	57 (203)	58 (211)	59 (203)
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.3 ± 4.4	27.6 ± 4.4	27.7 ± 4.3	27.3 ± 4.5	26.6 ± 4.2
Daily smoking	16 (233)	18 (66)	18 (64)	17 (61)	12 (42)
Arterial CVD	15 (212)	16 (58)	12 (42)	17 (60)	15 (52)
Cancer diagnosis					
<i>n</i>	300	62	79	71	88
Age (y)	69.2 ± 10.2	68.3 ± 10.9	69.9 ± 9.1	67.3 ± 10.5	70.6 ± 10.4
Sex (female)	42 (126)	44 (27)	46 (36)	38 (27)	41 (36)
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.0 ± 4.0	27.7 ± 4.2	28.5 ± 4.3	28.0 ± 3.6	27.7 ± 4.0
Daily smoking	16 (47)	27 (17)	16 (13)	7 (5)	14 (12)
Arterial CVD	17 (51)	16 (10)	20 (16)	15 (11)	16 (14)

Values are mean ± SD or % (*n*).

BMI, body mass index; CVD, cardiovascular disease.

A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the impact of different definitions of the active cancer period on the risk estimates. The analysis evaluated different durations for the active cancer period: 6 months before diagnosis to 2 years after diagnosis, at diagnosis to 2 years after diagnosis, at diagnosis to 5 years after diagnosis, and 1 year before diagnosis to 5 years after diagnosis. All analyses were performed using R version 4.3.2 (The R Foundation for Statistical Computing).

3 | RESULTS

The baseline characteristics of the subcohort, categorized by miR-145-5p quartiles, are presented in [Table 1](#). Among subcohort members who remained cancer free throughout the follow-up period, those with miR-145-5p levels in Q4 were on average older (65.9 ± 14.6 years) than those in Q1 (63.6 ± 14.1 years). Overall, the cancer-free subcohort had a higher proportion of females (58%), and the percentage of females across miR-145-5p quartiles varied only slightly (57%-59%), reflecting the use of sex-specific quartiles. BMI was marginally lower in Q4 than that in Q1 (26.6 ± 4.2 vs 27.6 ± 4.4 kg/m²). Daily smoking was lower in Q4 (12%) than that in Q1 (18%), while arterial CVD history showed no notable differences across quartiles.

Among subcohort participants that developed cancer (*n* = 300), individuals in Q4 had a slightly higher mean age (70.6 ± 10.4 years) than those in Q1 (68.3 ± 10.9 years). The proportion of females was 42% and ranged from 38% (Q3) to 46% (Q2) across miR-145-5p quartiles. BMI and arterial CVD history showed minimal differences, while the proportion of daily smoking declined from 27% in Q1

to 14% in Q4. Overall, the cancer subcohort was, on average, older, had a lower proportion of females, and had similar proportion of daily smoking than the cancer-free subcohort. [Supplementary Figure S1](#) compares the proportion of females across miR-145-5p quartiles using sex-specific and regular (ie, sex-unspecific) quartiles. With regular quartiles, females comprised 70% in Q4 and 44% in Q1, which corroborates previous reports on higher levels of miR-145 in women than that in men [17].

The characteristics of all patients with cancer (*n* = 437) at the time of cancer diagnosis are shown in [Table 2](#). This table includes both subcohort members and VTE cases who obtained a cancer diagnosis during the follow-up time. The age at cancer diagnosis was 74 years, and 43% were females. The distribution of cancer stages at diagnosis was 32% local, 31% regional metastasis, 21% distant metastasis, 11% unknown, and 5% not applicable (hematological cancers). The most common cancer sites were prostate (18%), colon (14%), and lung (10%). The distribution of cancers categorized as other are described in [Supplementary Table S2](#).

[Table 3](#) shows the characteristics of the 95 CAT cases and 340 non-CAT cases. Patients with CAT were slightly older than patients without CAT and had a higher prevalence of pulmonary embolism. Additionally, 31% of the CAT cases had another provoking factor besides cancer, while 37% of non-CAT cases were provoked. Surgery was the most common provoking factor in both groups, present in 24% of the CAT and 19% of the non-CAT cases.

The HRs of VTE across quartiles of plasma miR-145-5p levels are shown in [Table 4](#). Although not statistically significant, patients with active cancer and plasma miR-145-5p levels in the highest quartile had 45% lower risk of CAT than patients with active cancer and miR-145-

TABLE 2 Patient characteristics at cancer diagnosis.

Characteristic	Values
N	437
Years to cancer	5.5 (2.9-8.5)
Age at cancer diagnosis (y)	74.0 ± 11.4
Sex (female)	43 (188)
Cancer stage	
Local	32 (141)
Regional metastasis	31 (135)
Distant metastasis	21 (91)
Unknown	11 (50)
Not applicable ^a	5 (20)
Cancer site	
Prostate	18 (77)
Colon	14 (60)
Non-small cell lung cancer	10 (45)
Breast	7 (29)
Rectal	7 (29)
Malignant melanoma	5 (22)
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	4 (19)
Bladder	3 (14)
Pancreatic	3 (14)
Kidney	3 (12)
Multiple myeloma	3 (12)
Ovarian	3 (12)
Stomach	3 (12)
Liver	3 (11)
Uterine	2 (10)
Brain	2 (9)
Leukemia	2 (9)
Cervical	1 (3)
Esophageal	1 (2)
Hodgkin lymphoma	0 (1)
Other	8 (35)

Values are median (IQR), mean ± SD, or % (n).

^a Hematologic cancers.

5p levels in the lowest quartile in a model adjusted for age, sex, BMI and arterial CVD (HR, 0.55; 95% CI, 0.25-1.20; $P_{\text{trend}} = .4$). With additional adjustment for cancer site (low-, intermediate-, and high-risk sites) and stage (localized vs nonlocalized; model 3), the risk estimate strengthened but did not reach statistical significance (HR, 0.48; 95% CI, 0.21-1.08; $P_{\text{trend}} = .3$). When cancer site and stage were modeled with full categorical details, the Q4 vs Q1 HR was 0.33 (95% CI, 0.14-0.80). Among participants without active cancer, the highest miR-145-5p

quartile was associated with a 52% lower risk of VTE (HR, 0.48; 95% CI, 0.33-0.69; $P_{\text{trend}} < .001$). When regular quartiles of miR-145-5p were used, the HR for CAT in Q4 vs Q1 was 0.55 (95% CI, 0.24-1.28) in model 3, while the HR for VTE in those without cancer remained essentially similar (Supplementary Table S3). When modelling plasma miR-145-5p levels as a continuous variable, the HR per 1 SD increase in miR-145-5p levels was 0.70 (95% CI, 0.52-0.96) for CAT (model 2) and 0.81 (95% CI, 0.72-0.91) for non-CAT (Model 2).

We performed a sensitivity analysis to assess how variations in the time period used to classify a VTE as cancer-associated could impact the results. Supplementary Figure S2 presents the HRs and 95% CI per 1-SD increase in miR-145-5p across different definitions of the active cancer period in models adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and arterial CVD (with additional adjustment for collapsed cancer site and stage in CAT models). The findings revealed consistency in the risk of CAT according to miR-145-5p levels, regardless of the period used to define active cancer.

4 | DISCUSSION

Our population-based case-cohort study is, to the best of our knowledge, the first to investigate the association between plasma miR-145-5p levels and risk of CAT. We found that higher miR-145-5p levels were associated with lowered risk of VTE. In the continuous model, 1-SD increase in miR-145-5p levels was associated with a significant 30% lower risk of CAT and a 19% lower risk of non-CAT. In quartile analyses, the highest versus lowest quartile of miR-145-5p was associated with 45% and 52% lower risk of CAT and non-CAT, respectively, reaching statistical significance for non-CAT but not for CAT in analyses adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and arterial CVD. Additional adjustment of cancer site and stage further lowered the risk estimate for quartile 4 vs quartile 1 in CAT. The inverse association between plasma miR-145-5p and CAT remained consistent across various definitions of the active cancer period. Our findings of a similar inverse association between plasma miR-145-5p levels and risk of CAT and non-CAT imply that miR-145-5p is a potential risk biomarker for both pathological scenarios and that miR-145-5p may be involved in regulating thrombogenic pathways that are common in CAT and non-CAT.

MicroRNAs have been proposed as potential biomarkers for CAT. In a recent review, Anijs et al. [16] highlighted the potential of miRNAs as risk biomarkers of CAT but also noted limitations in prior studies, such as small sample sizes and post-diagnostic blood sampling. In the present study, we addressed these limitations by using a case-cohort design in a large, unselected population and measured miR-145-5p levels in plasma samples collected before VTE diagnosis. Consequently, miR-145-5p was evaluated as a risk/susceptibility biomarker [32], aligning with the etiological focus of our study. In this context, the use of relative rather than absolute risk estimates, along with treating death as a censoring event rather than a competing event, are appropriate methodological choices [33]. Our results expand on prior findings of an inverse association between miR-145-

TABLE 3 Characteristics of patients with and without VTE and active cancer at VTE diagnosis.

Characteristic	CAT (n = 95)	Non-CAT (n = 340)
Years to VTE	4.1 (2.6-5.6)	4.3 (2.1-5.9)
Age at VTE diagnosis (y)	71.8 ± 11.3	68.9 ± 14.4
Sex (female)	53 (50)	52 (176)
VTE type		
Deep vein thrombosis	38 (36)	46 (156)
Pulmonary embolism	62 (59)	54 (184)
Provoked ^a		
Surgery	24 (23)	19 (65)
Trauma	4 (4)	16 (55)
Acute medical condition	3 (3)	4 (15)
Immobilization	7 (7)	5 (17)
Other provoking factor(s)	2 (2)	4 (14)

Values are median (IQR), mean ± SD, or % (n).

VTE, venous thromboembolism.

^a Provoked by factors other than cancer. A VTE case might have multiple provoking factors.

5p levels and overall VTE risk in the general population [17], by showing that this inverse association holds when restricted to active cancer. As miR-145-5p has both tumor-suppressor [34] and antithrombotic properties [20], its utility might extend beyond its potential use not only as a risk biomarker for CAT but also as a gateway to widen the understanding of the underlying mechanisms of CAT.

Despite the established tumor-suppressor properties of miR-145-5p [34], higher miR-145-5p levels were recently shown to be associated with an increased risk of future cancer [35]. Yet, individuals with elevated miR-145-5p levels in the active cancer group exhibited a lower risk of CAT, despite cancer itself being a known risk factor for VTE. This observation suggests that even though the risk reduction associated with miR-145-5p were similar for CAT and non-CAT, the pathways through which miR-145-5p influences VTE risk may differ depending on the presence or absence of cancer. However, miR-145-5p targets several key genes in hemostasis, including TF [20], PAI-1 [21] and FXI [22], which are involved in pathways common to both cancer and VTE [23,24]. Speculating on pathways in observational studies requires caution, as unaccounted factors such as feedback regulations, dilution effects, and interactions between pathways add significant complexity. It is likely that all 3 factors of the hemostatic system (TF, PAI-1, and FXI) along with other gene targets of miR-145-5p act simultaneously, with their individual contributions to VTE varying in CAT and non-CAT.

As a shared mechanism between cancer and VTE, the TF pathway is thought to play an important role in CAT [36]. In a stasis model, systemic delivery of miR-145-5p reduced thrombus weight in a dose-dependent manner, mediated by TF downregulation, with *in vitro* experiments suggesting direct regulation of TF expression via

its 3' untranslated region [20]. Tumor cells express and release excessive amounts of TF [37,38], augmenting the role of TF for VTE in cancer. Of note, a meta-analysis showed that TF-bearing micro-particles are associated with increased risk of VTE in patients with cancer [39]. This could influence plasma miR-145-5p levels through at least 2 mechanisms. The first is a self-regulatory process in which cells might upregulate miR-145-5p production in response to elevated TF levels. The second is a so-called dilution effect in which higher target abundance (eg, TF expression) decreases the regulation efficiency of miRNAs [40]; hence, elevated TF levels in cancer might weaken the downregulatory function of miR-145-5p for TF. Although we observed similar risk estimates for CAT and non-CAT, the presence of these mechanisms underscores the need for caution in interpreting the results.

The impact of miR-145-5p on FXI levels may provide an alternative explanation for our findings. A Mendelian randomization study concluded that targeting FXI could reduce VTE risk [41], and a phase 2 clinical trial demonstrated that FXI inhibition prevented postoperative VTE [42]. miR-145-5p is proposed as a natural FXI inhibitor, as overexpression of miR-145-5p reduces FXI-3' untranslated region luciferase activity, identifying FXI as a target [22]. TF-induced coagulation is amplified by FXI [43], but this function becomes less critical when TF levels are abundant, as would be expected in active cancer. In a study on tumor cell-induced coagulation, FXI inhibition was found to disrupt coagulation only at low TF levels [24]. Interestingly, a recent case-control study showed that patients with cancer with FXI deficiency had lower rates of CAT than cancer-matched controls [44]. Thus, it might be speculated that regulation of FXI levels by miR-145-5p could partly explain the lowered VTE risk observed in our study, in both the presence and absence of active cancer.

PAI-1, a major endogenous inhibitor of fibrinolysis, has also been proposed as a target for miR-145-5p [21]. An inverse correlation between miR-145-5p and PAI-1 expression levels was observed in biopsies from normal and malignant bladder cancer tissues [21]. While elevated PAI-1 levels seem to support tumor progression in various cancers [45-47] and are associated with CAT [48], increased levels of PAI-1 persist as a risk factor for VTE also in the absence of cancer. Of note, the 4G/5G polymorphism in its promoter region has been linked to an increased risk of VTE [49], and a nested case-control study showed an increased risk of future VTE with higher PAI-1 levels, even after excluding participants with cancer [50]. These findings suggest that PAI-1 may play a role in mediating the relationship between miR-145-5p and VTE, potentially contributing to the observed risk reductions in both the cancer and noncancer groups.

Strengths of this study include robust validation of cancer and VTE events and a population-derived sample representative of disease prevalence and characteristics. Approximately 21% of VTE cases were CAT, consistent with registry data [51], and the distribution of VTE types, provoking factors, cancer stages, and sites aligned with findings from a large Scandinavian cohort [52]. Time-dependent modeling accounted for risk variation around cancer

TABLE 4 Hazard ratios (HRs) with 95% CIs for venous thromboembolism among participants with active cancer and those without, by increasing (sex-specific) quartiles (Q) of plasma miR-145-5p levels, and with miR-145-5p defined as a continuous variable.

miR-145-5p	Person years	Events	Model 1, HR (95 % CI)	Model 2, HR (95 % CI)	Model 3, HR (95% CI)
Active cancer		CAT			
Q1	112	29	Reference	Reference	Reference
Q2	142	16	0.31 (0.14-0.70)	0.30 (0.13-0.70)	0.24 (0.09-0.59)
Q3	123	25	0.61 (0.28-1.34)	0.65 (0.30-1.42)	0.49 (0.20-1.15)
Q4	154	25	0.55 (0.26-1.20)	0.55 (0.25-1.20)	0.48 (0.21-1.08)
Per 1-SD increase ^a	531	95	0.70 (0.52-0.94)	0.70 (0.52-0.96)	0.64 (0.47-0.88)
Cancer free		Non-CAT			
Q1	3483	113	Reference	Reference	—
Q2	3346	83	0.74 (0.54-1.02)	0.73 (0.53-1.01)	—
Q3	3373	91	0.75 (0.54-1.03)	0.75 (0.55-1.04)	—
Q4	3264	51	0.45 (0.31-0.65)	0.48 (0.33-0.69)	—
Per 1 SD increase ^a	13 466	338	0.80 (0.71-0.90)	0.81 (0.72-0.91)	—

Model 1: adjusted for age and sex. Model 2: adjusted for age, sex, body mass index, and arterial cardiovascular disease. Model 3: adjusted for age, sex, body mass index, arterial cardiovascular disease, high-risk cancer sites, and localized cancer stage.

^a One SD of log-transformed and normalized miR-145-5p levels = 0.67.

diagnosis [27], and sensitivity analyses using different periods showed consistent risk estimates. Quartile-based analyses displayed an inverse association between miR-145-5p levels and CAT risk, but the risk estimates did not reach statistical significance. As the number of CAT events were limited ($n = 95$), the lack of statistically significant results in quartile-based analysis might be attributed to low statistical power in the CAT group. However, other possibilities such as nonlinearity or threshold effects cannot be ruled out. Another important difference between the 2 groups is the baseline risk. Prior data from a Scandinavian population-based study estimated an incidence rate of 15 per 1000 person-years for CAT and 1.2 per 1000 person-years for non-CAT, respectively [53]. Consequently, an HR of similar size in CAT and non-CAT would correspond to a considerably higher absolute risk difference in CAT than that in non-CAT. The study was not powered for subgroup analyses by cancer or VTE type. Given that the association between plasma miR-145-5p and future cancer differs by cancer type [35], it is also plausible that the risk of CAT by miR-145-5p varies by cancer type. This heterogeneity may also explain the lack of a clear dose-dependent relationship in the risk estimates when analyzed by quartiles. Nonetheless, identifying universal CAT risk biomarkers would facilitate future clinical implementation and improve thromboprophylaxis management in patients with cancer. As the study cohort is predominantly of European/White ancestry, external generalizability to more ethnically diverse populations may be limited.

In conclusion, this population-based case-cohort study found that high plasma miR-145-5p levels were associated with a lower risk of CAT. Our findings suggest that miR-145-5p has the potential to serve as a risk biomarker for CAT, potentially through regulating common pathways in CAT and VTE unrelated to cancer.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conception and design: J.-B.H. and S.K.B. Inclusion of patients and data collection: K.H., J.-B.H., and S.K.B. Analysis of laboratory parameters: J.-B.H. and S.K.B. Statistical analyses: C.A. Interpretation of results: C.A., J.O., R.H., P.M., V.M.M., S.K.B., and J.-B.H. Draft of the manuscript: C.A. Critical revision of the manuscript: J.O., R.H., P.M., V.M.M., K.H., S.K.B., and J.-B.H. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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